

Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Business Education Curriculum: Its Impact on Entrepreneurial Readiness and Mindset

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence Technology (AIT) is reshaping industries, creating new opportunities, and redefining the skills required for business and entrepreneurial achievements. Integrating AIT into the business education curriculum is important because it is a major driver of change in the business world. Many industries are using AI to improve decision making, reduce costs, and create new products and services. This study examines the integration of AI learning into business education curriculum and its impact on students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. Three research questions were formulated for the study. Mixed method research design was adopted for the study and questionnaire was designed and administered to a population which include 377 respondents comprising 325 business education students and 52 business education lecturers in Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants who have engaged with AI-integrated courses. A reliability test was also conducted and analyzed using Cronbach Alpha coefficient method on the instrument which yielded an overall reliability coefficient of 0.88. Data generated was analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) using Descriptive, Person Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Regression Analysis (RA). The findings reveal that indicated that there is no or a very low extent of AIT integration into business education curriculum such that lecturers and students are not exposed to the knowledge and use of AIT in business education programme. The results of the study also reveal that artificial intelligence in business education curriculum significantly correlates and predicts entrepreneurial readiness and mindset, with emphasis on the relevance and impact of AIT incorporation in business education programs, focusing on its role in equipping students with essential entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. The paper concludes that integrating AIT into business education prepares an opportunity-driven students ready to meet modern entrepreneurship demands and gain competitive advantage after graduation. It is recommended that business education programs should incorporate AIT-focused courses and practical applications into their curriculum and business educators must undergo continuous professional development and training in AIT.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Business Education Curriculum, Entrepreneurial Readiness and Mindset.

Introduction

The rapid advancements in artificial intelligence technologies (AIT), have disrupted traditional education systems, necessitating the integration of emerging technologies into curricula to prepare students for the dynamic global market. Business education, being at the forefront of preparing future entrepreneurs and leaders, is experiencing a paradigm shift with AIT integration. This shift

not only transforms pedagogical approaches but also influences students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. Godwin et. al (2025) further defined the application as It is a part of computer science that develops and manages smart technology, designed to think, make decisions, and perform tasks automatically without constant human control, helping people by working independently and carrying out actions on their behalf. For the purpose of this study, AI is defined as an algorithm-based application that mimic human thought process using the power of advanced mainframes (supercomputers) to provide actionable solution for man and machine. By being able to mimic and replicate human intelligence, AI instigates the seamless performance Tasks like solving problems, understanding and using human language, and making decisions quickly and accurately with a high level of accuracy and effectiveness. Russell et al. (2021) Artificial Intelligence is the study of smart systems, called agents, that get information from their surroundings, understand it, and then take actions based on what they learn to achieve specific goals or solve problems effectively. AIT is the smart ability of a machine or computer that allows it to replicate or act like human skills, such as thinking, learning, and solving problems. It is a process of designing the computers, robots, or software to think intelligently, similar to humans. This involves learning by gathering information, reasoning by applying rules to draw conclusions, and improving through self-correction, helping them perform tasks more effectively and solve problems with greater accuracy and adaptability. Similarly, AIT encompasses a variety of subfields, such as machine learning (ML), natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, and robotics (Russell & Norvig, 2021). The goal is to make machines capable of doing tasks that usually need human intelligence, like solving problems, making decisions, and understanding language, so they can work more effectively and assist people in different activities. Elhajjar, et al (2021) encourages adopting AIT into education so that students can gain important skills for future jobs and the digital world, including creativity, innovation, and design thinking, helping them succeed and stay prepared for modern challenges. Investing in people to learn and use AIT tools is important for society's growth, even though many still doubt or misunderstand how AIT supports human activities, especially its usefulness in improving education and learning (Antonenko and Abramowitz, 2023). Fundamentally, AIT systems can observe their surroundings, identify objects, help in making decisions, solve difficult problems, learn from previous experiences, and copy patterns. By combining these abilities, they can perform tasks such as driving cars safely or recognizing faces to unlock mobile phones and other smart devices. AIT offers practical solutions to difficult problems in society, allowing students to connect with global issues and build important real-life problem-solving skills. It helps them think critically, create ideas, and prepare for future challenges in today's fast-changing world (Southworth et al., 2023). AIT has significantly increased productivity in various sectors by automating repetitive and time-consuming tasks. For instance, in industries like manufacturing and healthcare, AIT-powered systems perform operations with precision and speed, reducing errors and operational costs (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). AIT systems analyse large volumes of data to generate actionable insights, aiding organizations in making informed decisions. For example, AIT-powered analytics tools assist businesses in understanding customer preferences, predicting market trends, and optimizing resources (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). In education, particularly in business education, integrating AIT into the curriculum presents opportunities to enhance students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. Although, automation has taken over simple, routine jobs, but AIT will affect higher-level professional careers. Its success will rely on having an educated workforce that can understand, manage, and work with these advanced technologies effectively (Sylte, 2023). In business education, using AIT has strong potential to help students build important

skills needed to succeed in today's fast-changing work world, preparing them for future careers and professional challenges effectively. The use of AIT can perform more than just enter data; it can also write messages, create different types of communication, and summarize reports in a clear and useful way (Pratt, 2023). Some of these services include customer feedback for similar products, trips, and even in areas whereby a phone can connect from email or overhear conversations (Pereira, 2023) The rapid advancement of AIT is transforming various sectors, including business and education. Integrating AIT-powered tools into teaching and learning process through the use of AIT platforms, students develop critical thinking, problem-solving and technological proficiency skills essential for thriving in the modern knowledge economy (Joshua & Apuru, 2025). In response to this trend, there is an urgent need to integrate AIT into the business education curriculum to equip students with the skills required to thrive in a technology-driven entrepreneurial ecosystem (Kuratko, 2016). However, the extent to which AIT integration in business education impacts students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset remains an area of concern.

Business education is part of vocational and technical education that trains people for careers in business, entrepreneurship, and office work. It helps learners gain the knowledge, skills, and abilities needed to succeed in managing businesses and professional workplaces. It focuses on developing skills, knowledge, and competencies that are essential for success in business-related occupations (Ementa & Alonta, 2021). It is a vital component of vocational and technical education that equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for careers in business, entrepreneurship, and office administration. It encompasses the teaching of business concepts, management principles, accounting, marketing, and the use of digital technologies in business operations (Obi & Obasi, 2021). Business education is integrated into different levels of the education system, including secondary schools, colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities. The curriculum is structured to meet the economic needs of the country by producing graduates who can function in both the public and private sectors (Okoye & Okechukwu, 2020). The business education curriculum in Nigeria refers to the structured content, learning objectives, instructional strategies, and evaluation methods designed to equip students with business-related knowledge and skills. The curriculum is developed in line with the national education policy and is regularly reviewed to align with technological advancements, industry demands, and global best practices. The business education curriculum refers to the organized body of knowledge, instructional materials, and assessment methods designed to provide students with business-related knowledge and skills (Federal Ministry of Education [FME], 2014).

According to Okoro (2022), business education curriculum covers various aspects of business, such as accounting, commerce, entrepreneurship, office management, and digital literacy. It aims to develop individuals who can contribute effectively to Nigeria's socio-economic development. At the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) level, business education is structured to prepare future teachers and business professionals. It offers two major options (Magaji & Nayaya, 2022). The Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) level business education is designed to train future teachers for secondary schools and technical colleges. The business education curriculum is a continuous process that involves careful planning and development. It includes choosing learning activities designed to help students achieve the goals and objectives of the program, ensuring they gain useful knowledge, practical skills, and experiences that prepare them for success in business and professional careers (Ementa & Alonta, 2021). The aim is to provide students with foundational business knowledge and practical skills that can lead to further studies or direct employment (Ayonmike, 2021). Also, business education curriculum is prepared to develop and improve

students' entrepreneurial abilities, digital and technological competencies for modern business operations for job creation and economic growth (Aliyu 2018, Eze & Okafor, 2020). Furthermore, business education curriculum prepares future teachers who will train students in business-related subjects at secondary and tertiary levels (Olawale, 2017). Although, many institutions lack financial resources and for modern business laboratories, ICT facilities and professionally trained business education lecturers and teachers (Aliyu, 2018, Onyesom & Ashibogwu, 2021). The business education curriculum plays a vital role in equipping students with the skills needed for employment, entrepreneurship, and economic development. However, continuous curriculum reform and investment in modern learning resources are necessary to keep up with global business and technological trends.

Entrepreneurship is the process of finding, creating, and running a business idea to make profit, while also accepting the financial risks and challenges that come with starting and managing the business successfully (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). It plays a critical role in economic development by creating employment, fostering innovation, and contributing to national income (Hisrich, Peters, & Shepherd, 2017). To succeed in entrepreneurship, individuals must possess both entrepreneurial readiness and an entrepreneurial mindset. These elements help entrepreneurs navigate challenges, seize opportunities, and sustain their businesses in competitive environments (Kuratko, 2016). Entrepreneurial readiness refers to the readiness of an individual to start and manage a business successfully. It encompasses the knowledge, skills, competencies, and resources necessary to embark on an entrepreneurial journey (Bacq & Janssen, 2011). According to Fatoki (2014), entrepreneurial readiness includes; acquiring relevant knowledge through formal and informal education, gaining practical skills such as financial management, leadership, and marketing, having access to startup capital and funding sources, possessing confidence, resilience, and a risk-taking attitude, building relationships with mentors, investors, and industry experts. Entrepreneurial readiness ensures that an individual has the necessary foundation to initiate and sustain a business (Neneh, 2012). The entrepreneurial mindset is a way of thinking that enables individuals to recognize and capitalize on opportunities, embrace innovation, and persist in the face of challenges (Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2019). It involves cognitive patterns, attitudes, and behaviours that foster entrepreneurial success.

According to Haynie et al. (2010), an entrepreneurial mindset includes the following characteristics: the ability to identify market gaps and potential business ideas, the ability to overcome failures and setbacks, creativity in problem-solving and business development, willingness to take calculated risks in uncertain environments, confidence in one's ability to achieve entrepreneurial goals. An entrepreneurial mindset is crucial for adapting to changing business environments and sustaining long-term business success (Dweck, 2006). Entrepreneurial readiness and mindset are interrelated. While readiness provides the necessary resources, knowledge, and skills, the mindset ensures that an entrepreneur can effectively apply these elements in dynamic business environments (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). For instance: A prepared entrepreneur with access to funding but lacking a risk-taking mindset may find it difficult to start a business. Equally, an individual with an entrepreneurial mindset but lacking financial readiness may struggle to sustain a business. Thus, both components are essential for entrepreneurial success (Minniti & Bygrave, 2001). Entrepreneurial readiness and mindset are critical for business success. Readiness ensures individuals have the necessary knowledge, skills, and resources, while mindset fosters innovation, resilience, and risk-taking. The combination of both elements determines an entrepreneur's ability to navigate business challenges and seize opportunities. For Nigeria and other developing

economies, fostering entrepreneurial readiness and mindset through education, training, and policy support can drive economic growth and job creation. Many business educators lack the necessary expertise to incorporate AIT-driven content into their teaching, and institutions often do not provide the required AIT tools or funding for curriculum updates (Aliyu, 2018). This further widens the gap between business education and industry expectations. Additionally, there is insufficient empirical research on the actual impact of AIT integration in business education on students' entrepreneurial mindset and readiness. While some studies suggest that exposure to AIT can enhance problem-solving skills, automation capabilities, and digital entrepreneurship activities (Makridakis, 2017). Although, lack of AIT integration in business education affects students' entrepreneurial mindset. AIT has the potential to enhance creativity, problem-solving, and adaptability key traits of successful entrepreneurs. However, in business education programmes, students are not encouraged to explore AIT-driven solutions, which may result in a rigid and risk-averse mindset. The fear of AIT replacing jobs rather than creating new opportunities further discourages students from embracing technology in entrepreneurship.

Statement of the Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligent Technologies (AIT) into the business education curriculum has become a necessity in today's rapidly evolving digital economy. AIT is transforming industries by automating processes, enhancing decision-making, and creating new business opportunities. As the business landscape becomes increasingly technology-driven, business education must adapt to ensure that students are adequately prepared for entrepreneurial success. However, the extent to which AIT is integrated into business education and its impact on students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset remains a significant challenge. One of the major concerns is that traditional business education curricula largely focus on theoretical knowledge and outdated business models, leaving students ill-equipped to navigate the digital-driven business environment. Many graduates struggle to apply AIT-based tools such as data analytics, machine learning, and automation in business decision-making, limiting their ability to innovate and compete in modern industries. Without exposure to AIT-driven business processes, students may find it difficult to recognize opportunities, develop data-driven solutions, and implement digital strategies in their entrepreneurial ventures. This gap in AIT knowledge and application reduces students' confidence in launching and sustaining technology-driven enterprises. Another challenge is the limited infrastructure and resources available for AIT education in business schools. Many institutions lack the necessary AIT-powered tools, software, and teaching materials to effectively integrate AIT into the curriculum. Given these challenges, it is crucial to examine how AIT can be effectively integrated into the business education curriculum and how this integration impacts students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. Addressing this issue will provide insights into curriculum reforms, teaching strategies, and policy recommendations that can enhance business education, empower students with relevant digital skills, and prepare them for technology-driven entrepreneurship.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to investigate the integration of artificial intelligence into business education curriculum as well as its impact on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. To achieve this, specific purposes of the study include to determine:

1. The extent of AIT integration in business education curriculum.
2. The perceived AIT tools needed for effective integration into business education curriculum.
3. The impact of AIT integration on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset.

4. The combined correlation of AIT integration with entrepreneurial readiness and mindset

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of AIT integration in business education curriculum?
2. What are the perceived AIT tools needed for effective integration into business education curriculum?
3. What is the impact of AIT integration on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset?
4. What is the combined correlation of AIT integration with entrepreneurial readiness and mindset?

Methodology

The design of the study was mixed method research design. The target population includes 377 respondents comprising 325 NCE three (3) students and 52 lecturers in Business Education programme. Purposive sampling technique was used for the study. Questionnaires was designed and distributed for data collection. A structured questionnaire is developed as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire consists of five sections: Demographics which include age and gender. While section two contains questionnaire items on the extent of AIT integration in business education curriculum, AIT tools needed for integration into business education curriculum, Entrepreneurial Readiness (EP) and entrepreneurial Mindset which provided item statements to assess the extents of respondent's readiness and readiness to use AIT tools including technical skills, infrastructure availability, and institutional support. AIT integration which items evaluate the extent of AIT integration, AIT needed tools in business education curriculum, Entrepreneurial Readiness (EP) and entrepreneurial Mindset provided the questionnaire items. The rating scale for the instrument was a four-point scale which include strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1). Three experts validated and the overall reliability of Instrument accounted for 0.88. The questionnaire is distributed both physically and electronically. The researcher briefed the participants on the aims and purpose of the study, and assured their confidentiality in the process of data collection and analysis. Descriptive statistics, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis and Regression Analysis (RA) were conducted using SPSS version 23. The decision rule for interpretation of the analysis was a mean score ranging from 0.10-2.49 was negative and disagreed while a mean score that range from 2.50-4.00 was positive and agreed.

Results of the Findings

Research Question 1: What is the extent of AIT integration in business education curriculum?

Table1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the extent of AIT integration in business education curriculum.

S/N	Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
1.	AI concepts are adequately included in the Business Education curriculum.	1.47	0.51	Disagree
2.	I have been taught how to use AI tools relevant to business processes (e.g., chatbots, analytics software).	1.38	0.48	Disagree
3.	My lecturers incorporate AI-related topics in their teaching materials and discussions.	1.46	0.51	Disagree
4.	The Business Education program prepares students to understand the ethical implications of AI in business.	1.33	0.58	Disagree
5.	AI applications are integrated into course assignments and practical exercises.	1.48	0.51	Disagree
6.	There are enough learning resources (books, software, labs) available for studying AI in business education.	1.55	0.50	Disagree
7.	AI is taught in a way that connects it to real-world business problems and case studies.	1.39	0.58	Disagree
8.	I feel confident about using AI tools for tasks such as data analysis, marketing automation, or business forecasting.	2.52	0.68	Agree
9.	Lecturers in my program are well-equipped and trained to teach AI-related content.	1.52	0.57	Disagree
10.	The curriculum encourages interdisciplinary learning by linking AI with business and technology.	1.51	0.56	Disagree
11.	I have participated in projects or simulations that required the use of AI to solve business challenges.	1.48	0.58	Disagree
12.	The integration of AI into the curriculum can improve my readiness for the modern business environment.	2.50	0.67	Agree
Overall		1.50	0.55	Agree

Key: \bar{X} =Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, Dec=Decision

The result presented in Table 1 showed that items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 had means ranging from 1.33-1.55 which are within the mean range of 0.01-2.49. This implied that the respondents disagree that AI concepts are adequately included in the business education curriculum (1.47), AI have been taught how to use AI tools relevant to business processes (1.38), lecturers incorporate AI-related topics in their teaching materials and discussions (1.46), the business education program prepares students to understand the ethical implications of AI in business (1.33), AI applications are integrated into course assignments and practical exercises (1.48), there are enough learning resources (books, software, labs) available for studying AI in business education (1.55), AI is taught in a way that connects it to real-world business problems and case studies (1.39), lecturers in my program are well-equipped and trained to teach AI-related content (1.52), the curriculum encourages interdisciplinary learning by linking AI with business and technology (1.51) and they have participated in projects or simulations that required the use of AI to solve business challenges (1.48). While items 8 and 12 had a mean of 2.52 and 2.50 which are within the mean range of 2.50-4.00, implying that they feel confident about using AI tools for tasks such as data analysis, marketing automation, or business forecasting (2.52) and the integration of AI into the curriculum

can improve their readiness for the modern business environment (2.50). The overall mean value of 1.50, indicated that there is no or a very low extent of AIT integration into business education curriculum such that lecturers and students are not exposed to the knowledge and use of AIT in business education programme. Furthermore, Table 1 showed that the standard deviation ranged from 0.49-0.67 with a variation of 0.18 which implied that the responses of the respondents were consistent and close to each other with high agreement and the value close to the mean.

Research Question 2: What are the perceived AIT tools needed for effective integration into business education curriculum?

Table1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the perceived AIT tools needed for effective integration into business education curriculum.

S/N	Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
1.	ChatGPT (OpenAI) is needed to assist students with business concepts, writing, and problem-solving.	3.38	0.49	Agree
2.	Squirrel AI is an intelligent tutoring system that personalizes learning based on student performance.	3.47	0.51	Agree
3.	GradeScope automated assessment and grading tool is needed to that helps instructors evaluate students efficiently.	3.46	0.50	Agree
4.	Tableau AI tool would help students analyse and visualize data for strategic decision-making.	3.33	0.68	Agree
5.	Power BI (Microsoft) data analytics tool that is needed to teach students data-driven business insights.	3.48	0.51	Agree
6.	Google Analytics is a web analytics tool that helps students understand digital marketing performance and customer behaviour	3.55	0.50	Agree
7.	UiPath robotic process automation (RPA) tool is needed to demonstrates how businesses automate repetitive tasks.	3.39	0.58	Agree
8.	Salesforce Einstein AI is a customer relationship management (CRM) tool that enables students to learn AI-driven sales and marketing automation.	3.52	0.66	Agree
9	Shopify AI e-commerce platform is needed to teach students about online business management.	3.52	0.57	Agree
10	Automation Anywhere is an automation platform that is needed to help students understand operational efficiency.	3.51	0.57	Agree
11	Copy.ai as a tool would help students generation create marketing copies and business content.	3.48	0.58	Agree
12	SimVenture business simulation platform that allows students to develop entrepreneurial skills through AI-driven decision-making scenarios.	3.50	0.67	Agree
Overall		3.47	0.29	Agree

Key: \bar{X} =Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, Dec=Decision

The result presented in Table 2 showed that all the items had means ranging from 3.33-3.55 which are within the mean range of 3.50-4.49. This implied that the respondents agree that ChatGPT (OpenAI) is needed to assist students with business concepts, writing, and problem-solving (3.38), Squirrel AI is an intelligent tutoring system that personalizes learning based on student performance

(3.47), GradeScope automated assessment and grading tool is needed to that helps instructors evaluate students efficiently (3.46), Tableau AI tool would help students analyse and visualize data for strategic decision-making (3.33), Power BI (Microsoft) data analytics tool that is needed to teach students data-driven business insights (3.48), Google Analytics is a web analytics tool that helps students understand digital marketing performance and customer behaviour (3.55), UiPath robotic process automation (RPA) tool is needed to demonstrates how businesses automate repetitive tasks (3.39), Salesforce Einstein AI is a customer relationship management (CRM) tool that enables students to learn AI-driven sales and marketing automation. (3.52), Shopify AI e-commerce platform is needed to teach students about online business management (3.52), Automation Anywhere is an automation platform that is needed to help students understand operational efficiency (3.51), Copy.ai as a tool would help students generation create marketing copies and business content (3.48) and SimVenture business simulation platform that allows students to develop entrepreneurial skills through AI-driven decision-making scenarios (3.50). The overall mean value of 3.47, indicated that AIT tools are needed to be integrated into business education curriculum such that entrepreneurial readiness and mindset of lecturers and students would be encouraged. Furthermore, Table 2 showed that the standard deviation ranged from 0.49-0.68 with a variation of 0.19 which implied that the responses of the respondents were consistent and close to each other with high agreement and the value close to the mean.

Research Question 3: What is the impact of AIT integration on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset?

Pearson Correlation Coefficient Analysis on Impact of AIT Integration on Entrepreneurial Readiness and Mindset

Variables		AIT	ER	EM
AIT	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	377		
ER	Pearson Correlation	.768**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	377	377	
EM	Pearson Correlation	.659**	.634**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	377	377	377

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Key: AIT=Artificial Intelligence Technology, ER=Entrepreneurial Readiness, EM=Entrepreneurial Mindset

Table 3 presents the result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the perceived impact of AIT integration on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. The result of Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of 0.768, n=377, p<.001 shows a positive impact of AIT on entrepreneurial readiness. While, the result of Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of 0.659, n=377, p<.001 also shows a positive impact of AIT on entrepreneurial mindset of business education lecturers and students respectively. This means that the needed AIT tools in business education curriculum correlates and predicts lecturers and students’ entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. The strong positive correlation indicates that as business education lecturers and students get to utilize AIT tools imbedded in the curriculum, there is a significant corresponding high increase in their entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. The revealed result shows a significance value (Sig. 2-tailed) for this correlation of 0.001, which is

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings was based on the results obtained in this study which are analyzed and presented in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. In research question one presented in Table 1, the results of the study show that respondents disagree that AI concepts are adequately included in the business education curriculum, AI have been taught how to use AI tools relevant to business processes, lecturers incorporate AI-related topics in their teaching materials and discussions, the business education program prepares students to understand the ethical implications of AI in business among others. Ultimately, the results of the study indicated that there is no or a very low extent of AIT integration into business education curriculum such that lecturers and students are not exposed to the knowledge and use of AIT in business education programme. The findings of the study exposed the missing gap of business education curriculum as found by a study of Ahmad et al. (2021), who stated that embedding AI-related competencies in educational curricula equips students with relevant skills, increasing their competitiveness in AI-driven job markets. Hence, AI into the business education curriculum equips students with future-ready skills, thereby improving their employability in a rapidly changing job market. Also, Dwivedi et al. (2021) argue that exposure to AI tools in education enables students to adapt to the digital transformation trends dominating modern industries. AI integration prepares business education students to navigate and manage technology-driven business environments. Eze et al. (2021) found that business graduates often lack digital competencies, creating a mismatch between educational outcomes and labour market expectations. This means that without AI integration, business education curricula risk becoming outdated and misaligned with industry demands. Song (2024) discusses the need for educational institutions to adapt to the demands of AI and deep learning, suggesting that students must learn to assess their professional abilities in an AI-driven landscape.

In research question two presented in Table 2, the result shows AIT tools are needed to be integrated into business education curriculum such that entrepreneurial readiness and mindset of lecturers and students would be encouraged. The needed AIT tools to be embedded into business education curriculum indicates that as lecturers and students get acquainted of AIT tools to prepare the minds for entrepreneurial activities. This is in agreement with Ore and Hassan (2023), that business curriculum content that contains AIT predict changes in the development of lecturers and students' entrepreneurial skills readiness and mindset. Based on the findings of this author, it was noted that Business Education curriculum content does not equip students with the required entrepreneurial skills needed to be self-reliant, as such, the curriculum content should be enriched and updated with current business contents including AIT-focused contents on a regular basis. This is in agreement with Hasan et. al. (2023) who stated that higher AIT knowledge and awareness increases significantly impact its integration into business education curriculum. Also, Giraud-Carrier et. al., (2021) highlighted the use of deliberate practice as a training technique to develop expertise in business education. Xu et. al. (2021), discuss the pedagogy and learning outcomes of AI in business curriculum, emphasizing the importance of incorporating AI into educational settings. Owoc et. al. (2021) identifies the benefits and challenges of implementing AI in education, providing strategies for higher education organizations to validate their design. Thurzo et. al. (2023) reviewed the impact of AI on dental education, emphasizing the need for curriculum updates to adapt to advancements in AI technology. Furthermore, Alexandra et. al. (2022) discusses the use of AI technology in developing adaptable curricula that align with job requirements in higher education. Song (2024) emphasizes the importance of exploring new business curriculum systems empowered by the digital economy, highlighting the challenges and opportunities presented by AI in talent cultivation in

higher education. Overall, the literature suggests a growing recognition of the need for integrating AI into business education curriculum to prepare students for the evolving demands of the digital economy.

However, the analysis for research question three was set to determine the perceived impact of AIT tools integration on entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. The result shows a positive impact of AIT tools integration into business education curriculum on entrepreneurial mindset of business education lecturers and students respectively. This means that the needed AIT tools in business education curriculum impact and predicts lecturers and students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. This is in agreement with Bui et. al., (2024) whose study stated that integration of AIT tools such as ChatGPT in business or entrepreneurship education, impact digital entrepreneurial intentions, readiness and mindset. This research contributes to understanding the dynamics of AI integration in entrepreneurship. The positive relationship indicates that as business education lecturers and students get to utilize AIT tools imbedded in the curriculum, there is a significant corresponding high impact in their entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. This is also in agreement with Usman et. al., (2024) who provided a critical review of AIT-driven strategies for entrepreneurial success and stated that AIT applications can impact individual entrepreneurship intentions and mindset. The study highlighted the benefits and challenges associated with integrated AIT in business education leads to entrepreneurial readiness and mindset that will transcend to entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, Indrasari et. al., (2023) in their study found that AIT integration into business education curriculum is an important factor that highly impact positively on both entrepreneurial readiness and mindset during or after the teaching and learning programme. The result of analysis for question four shows that reveals that the combination of ER and EM indeed significantly correlates with AIT integration in business education curriculum. These results suggest that AIT integration into business education curriculum play a crucial role in determining lecturers and students' ER and EM. Therefore, business education curriculum would seek to integrate AIT in other to promote lecturers' and students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. This study agrees with Haynie et al. (2010), studied and found that AIT tools integration into business education curriculum correlates with entrepreneurial, intentions, readiness and mindset. The author emphasized that lack of imbedding AIT tool into business education curriculum may decrease the level entrepreneurial readiness and mindset of lecturers and students. Similarly, in a study by Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, (2000), it was highlighted that AIT integration in education is important in influencing ER and EM. Furthermore, Moravec et. al., (2024) studied and found that entrepreneurial readiness and mindset in utilization of AIT is very important across various domains of businesses.

Conclusion

This study set out to examine the integration of AIT into business education curriculum and its impact on students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. One of the most significant impacts of AIT integration is the development of entrepreneurial readiness among students. The findings reveal that AIT tools are needed to be integrated into business education curriculum. Furthermore, AIT facilitates personalized learning experiences that cater to individual students' strengths and weaknesses, enabling them to develop the confidence needed to take on entrepreneurial challenges. The integration of artificial intelligence technology (AIT) into the business education curriculum has the potential to revolutionize the learning experience, equipping students with the necessary skills to thrive in the digital economy. The study reveals that AIT integration into business education would have impact on students' and lecturers' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. By embedding

AIT in business education, institutions can bridge the gap between traditional learning approaches and the evolving demands of the global labour market, ensuring that graduates are adequately prepared for entrepreneurial ventures and innovative business practices.

Therefore, integrating AIT into the business education curriculum is a transformative step toward preparing students for entrepreneurial success. It enhances their problem-solving abilities, fosters innovation, and equips them with future-ready skills needed in the AIT-driven business world. While challenges exist, a well-structured AIT-integrated curriculum, supported by faculty development and technological investment, can significantly improve students' entrepreneurial readiness and mindset. Ultimately, AIT integration in business education is not just a trend but a necessity for cultivating the next generation of innovative and tech-savvy entrepreneurs. The findings of this research contribute to the growing body of knowledge on educational technology adoption and offer practical recommendations for policymakers and educators aiming to leverage AIT in business education.

Recommendations

Business education programs should incorporate AIT-focused courses and practical applications into their curriculum. This includes subjects such as AIT-driven business analytics, automation in entrepreneurship, and machine learning for business decision-making. Institutions should also integrate AIT tools to provide students with hands-on experience. This will help develop their problem-solving abilities, data-driven decision-making skills, and innovative thinking, which are essential for entrepreneurial success.

To effectively teach AIT concepts and their business applications, business educators must undergo continuous professional development and training in AIT. Universities and colleges should invest in AIT-driven teaching resources, including smart classrooms, cloud computing tools, and AIT-powered learning platforms. By providing faculties and departmental members with the necessary skills and infrastructure to ensure effective AIT integration and bridge the knowledge gap in business education.

Educational institutions should establish partnerships with technology firms, AIT startups, and business organisations to provide students with real-world exposure to AIT applications in entrepreneurship. Internship programs, AIT-powered business competitions, and mentorship opportunities should be integrated into the curriculum to enhance students' entrepreneurial mindset. Engaging students in real-time AIT-driven business projects will both boost their readiness for the job market and also encourage them to leverage AIT for innovative business ventures.

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